

Citation for the Presentation of the
2005 ICPE Medal to

Professor Svein Sjoberg

University of Oslo, Norway

Presented in Delhi, India, 2005

Svein Sjoberg has had a long and distinguished career in Science and Technology Education, with particular attention to the role of Physics Education in a broad science education. Svein Sjoberg began his scientific career with a PhD in experimental nuclear physics. He brought to science and technology education the rigorous thinking of a physicist allied to an understanding of psychological and social factors. It is crucial that distinguished physics educators like Svein participate in the development and definition of Science and Technology Education.

He turned from an early interest in students' conceptions, to the much broader field of social relations and science education, including important studies of gender differences, and of social and cultural differences. He has had a long-standing concern for girls in science education, particularly in relation to Physics Education. Svein Sjoberg was one of the first to see that international comparisons of standards such as TIMSS needed urgently to be complemented by international studies of attitudes to and responses to science, and one of the very first to act upon that understanding on a global scale through research. Two remarkable studies, SAS Science and Society – cross cultural study of factors of relevance for teaching and learning of science and technology, and its follow-up, ROSE Relevance of Science Education, have been notable for the very wide international participation that they achieved.

Besides Svein Sjoberg's high standing in science education in the Nordic countries and in Europe, even more important is the world-wide international impact of his work, which has obtained valuable and convincing results from international comparisons, and at the same time has helped researchers in Africa, Asia and other countries to raise the standards of their research through active participation in these studies. He is chair of IOSTE, and a member of AFCLIST (African Forum for Children's Literacy in Science and Technology).

It is this international aspect of his work throughout the world, together with its high quality and important and meaningful results, which is the particular focus for the award of the ICPE medal.

